

Hydrostatic Pressure Effect on martensite transition and Magnetocaloric Properties of Ni_{1.75}Pt_{0.25}MnGa Heusler alloy.

M. Kannan¹, S. Arumugam^{1*}, Sanjay Singh², K. Manikandan¹, L. Govindaraj¹

¹ Centre for High Pressure Research, School of Physics, Bharathidasan University, Tiruchirappalli-620024, India.

² School of Materials Science and Technology, Indian Institute of Technology (BHU) Varanasi-221005, India.

Abstract:

The effect of hydrostatic pressure on the magnetic and Magnetocaloric properties of Ni_{1.75}Pt_{0.25}MnGa shape memory Heusler alloy around the martensitic transition has been investigated. We find that the application of hydrostatic Pressure increases the martensitic transition temperature (T_M) for Ni_{1.75}Pt_{0.25}MnGa by $dT_M/dP = +3.89$ K/GPa and therefore pressure stabilizes the martensite phase. This phenomenon could be accounted for as follows. Increase of pressure would reduce the unit cell volume, which influences T_M and other characteristic transition temperatures. With increasing pressure from 0.32GPa to 0.95Gpa blocking temperature is shifted from 200 K to 250K. The maximum magnetic entropy change (ΔS_{max}) is found to be reduced from 9.29 J Kg⁻¹ K⁻¹ to 5.48 J Kg⁻¹ K⁻¹ around T_M for Ni_{1.75}Pt_{0.25}MnGa and RCP increases linearly with the application of field upto 0.91GPa but the maximum RCP decreases with the application of pressure upto 9 GPa. Magneto crystalline anisotropy possibly arises due to the volume change by increase in hydrostatic pressure.

References:

1. Singh Sanjay, D'Souza S W, Mukherjee K, Kushwaha P, Barman S R, AgarwalSandeep, Mukhopadhyay P K, ChakrabartiAparna and Sampathkumaran E V Appl. Phys. Lett. 104 231909(2014).
2. Liu Jian, GottschalTino, Skokov Konstantin P, Moore James D and Gutfleisch Oliver Nature Materials. 11 620(2012)
3. Han Z D, Wang D H, Zhang C L, Tang S L, Gu B X and Du Y W Appl. Phys. Lett. 89, 182507 (2006).
4. Marcos J, Planes A, Manosa L, Casanova F, Batlle X, Labarta A and Martinez B Phys. Rev. B. 66, 224413 (2002).
5. Moya X, Manosa L, Planes A, Aksoy S, Acet M, Wassermann E F and Krenke T Phys. Rev. B 75 184412(2007)